

Spring rituals of Ukrainians in the Republic of Moldova: general characteristics

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According to the field material and sources collected by us, the Ukrainian population of the Republic of Moldova has preserved many traditional elements of spring rituals to this day.

Pre-Easter Christian rituals are closely intertwined with pre-Christian beliefs and are permeated with motives of the meeting of spring, the rebirth of nature, saturated with agrarian, marriage and child-bearing magic. The holiday Стрітення with the corresponding ritual actions, folk signs, fortune-telling is associated with the cleansing cults of water and fire, preparations for spring field work. The holidays Явдо́хи, Со́рок святи́х, Те́плого Оле́кси are distinguished by characteristic rituals and signs. The fragmentary preserved ancient ritual Коло́дка / Колоді́й, associated with the holiday Пу́щення and initiating marriage, has archaic roots. Благові́щення is associated with imitation of magic, girlish round dances (весня́нки / гаї́вки), youthful fun, children's games. An integral attribute of this period is the 40-day church Great Post – Великий пі́ст.

The dominant feature of Easter rituals is the holiday of the Resurrection of Christ (Па́ска / Вели́кдень), which is preceded by Palm Sunday (Шу́ткова / Ве́рбна / Зелена́ неді́ля) and Holy Week (Шу́ткова / Вербна / Зелена́ неді́ля). Pre-Easter preparations and Easter rituals (the consecration of willow branches, the preparation and symbolism of Easter ritual dishes (кра́шанка, пі́санка, па́ска / перепі́чка) and ritual actions with them, collecting an Easter basket, Easter lights, a festive Easter meal, etc.) are characterized by strict observance of the Christian and pre-Christian ritualism, as well as a pronounced regional and local specificity, clear regulation and corresponding attributes.

The post-Easter ritualism of the holidays of St. George (Ю́рія / Гео́рґія), Рахма́нський Вели́кдень is rich in agrarian, pastoral and erotic rituals. The final holiday of the spring cycle is Ascension (Вознесі́нє, Вознесі́ння).